

Research Article

Spatial and temporal exploration of NDVI, LAI, and SMI in coniferous forests: Detecting changes in Parangalitsa Reserve

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Abstract

This study develops a framework based on three indices—Soil Moisture Index (SMI), Leaf Area Index (LAI), and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), and analyzes their spatial variation across the Parangalitsa Reserve from 2015 to 2024. While spectral indices like NDVI and LAI are well-established tools for monitoring Earth's processes, this research goes beyond their general application by tailoring these indices to the specific context of a high-value protected area. The framework is designed to identify areas with significant deviations in index values over time, which may signal ecological changes influenced by both natural and anthropogenic factors. By relating these deviations with land cover, slope inclination, and aspect, this study introduces a more holistic perspective to uncover meaningful patterns. The results reveal an overlap of deviations in the indices, particularly within coniferous forest areas, highlighting potential regions for targeted in-situ observations. This approach can improve forest management and monitoring by providing a framework for identifying ecologically sensitive areas. The research emphasizes the utility of proven spectral indices when integrated into a targeted, site-specific framework that contributes to forest management and ecological monitoring by providing a replicable methodology for pre-assessing sensitive ecosystems. By enabling a deeper understanding of localized dynamics, the study bridges the gap between well-documented methodologies and their practical application in safeguarding biodiversity and ecosystem services in protected areas.

Key words: Forest monitoring, remote sensing, sustainable management, vegetation indices

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1. Introduction

Parangalitsa Reserve (1450–1950 m a.s.l.) is the second oldest reserve in Bulgaria, established in 1933 (Council of Ministers 1933). It is representative of the range of conditions typical for Norway spruce (*Picea abies* (L.) Karst.) ecosystems across Central and Eastern Europe (Panayotov et al. 2015). Strict prohibitions of human intervention and management activities in these forests allowed for the natural development of heterogeneous forest structures (Dountchev et al. 2016). This resulted in the establishment and enhancement of natural regeneration processes (Panayotov et al. 2011), fostering a self-sustaining and ecologically resilient forest ecosystem. Norway spruce forests are among

the most susceptible to natural disturbances in Europe (Tsvetanov et al. 2018). Over the past 150 years, in the Parangalitsa Reserve, the wind has been the primary disturbance agent, causing medium to large windthrows (Panayotov et al. 2011). These were followed by subsequent bark beetle outbreaks, which were limited by the high altitude and the higher structural heterogeneity (Dountchev et al. 2016). Forest fires have had an insignificant impact affecting only 4% of the territory (Panayotov et al. 2011).

In general, *P. abies*, while economically important, is highly sensitive to climate change (D'Andrea et al. 2023). Its shallow, horizontal root system makes it particularly vulnerable to fluctuations in soil moisture, contributing to its susceptibility to windthrow and other disturbances (Gaul et al. 2008). At higher elevations (>1400 m), *P. abies* exhibits greater drought resistance, though this is often coupled with reduced recovery rates (Popa et al. 2024). Dendrochronological studies in Parangalitsa further reveal that Norway spruce growth is relatively unaffected by climate variability under optimal conditions. However, trees subjected to intense competition for resources demonstrate increased sensitivity to summer droughts and atypical climate patterns (Panayotov et al. 2016b). The dynamic changes in the health of forest vegetation within the reserve boundaries have been a topic of considerable scientific interest (Ivanov and Tyufekchiev 2019). Moreover, the reserve is home to old-growth mixed fir-beech-spruce forests, characterized by a very active process of gap formation and also one of the most productive forests in Bulgaria, especially in the lower-elevation parts (Asenova et al. 2019). A holistic view of the ongoing vegetation changes could provide important insight on where to focus scientific endeavor. Remote sensing offers a diverse range of applications like change detection and monitoring of endangered territories (Todorov and Kirilov 2022), forest ecology, including vegetation structure, vegetation chemistry and moisture, biodiversity, soil characteristics and more (Lechner et al. 2020). The spatial distribution of different vegetation indices is a source of valuable insights into the variability of environmental conditions (Raufu 2024). The Normal Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) has been used for decades and is one of the most popular indices for assessing the condition of vegetation for various purposes (Sarafova 2021). NDVI is widely used to monitor vegetation density and vigor, and its sensitivity to soil moisture and temperature makes it a valuable tool in understanding forest responses to environmental stressors such as drought (Adhikari et al. 2024). Soil moisture is a critical factor for vegetation growth, influencing hydrological cycles and energy balance. It is often monitored using indices like NDVI and more complex drought indices, which integrate soil moisture and vegetation health parameters (Tao et al. 2021; Habiboullah and Louly 2023). Remote sensing techniques also offer a continuous estimation of soil moisture for a large area by referring to the changes in biophysical factors, such as surface energy balance and vegetation cover, which were affected by the availability of soil water (Tajudin et al. 2021). Another interesting variable is the Leaf area index (LAI), which measures leaf area per ground surface area, which is a key indicator of forest canopy health and productivity, affecting energy and water exchange between the land surface and atmosphere and is essential for predicting light conditions, assessing total above-ground biomass, and calculating the primary productivity of vegetation (Parker 2020). Contemporary technologies offer even more tools, methods and sources for remote

sensing monitoring of forest ecology (Wang et al. 2024). Nevertheless, each of these indices—SMI (Soil Moisture Index), LAI and NDVI, serves to understand different aspects of forest ecosystems, from health and productivity to impacts from external and internal disturbances. Therefore, the present article explores the application of the combination of these three indices for identifying forest areas that show indications of undergoing changes in their ecology. By calculating SMI, LAI and NDVI for the territory of Parangalitsa Reserve for the period 2015–2024 and after investigating their correlation, the changes of each of the indices for this period are detected and then overlaid. The hypothesis is that the territories with unstable parameters may be strongly influenced by external or internal disturbances. This information could guide targeted in-situ observations by identifying strategic areas for monitoring. Ultimately, such integrated monitoring can provide a more comprehensive understanding of forest dynamics and enhance the management of ecologically sensitive regions. This model of assessment is open to integrating more spatial information sources and to make further contribution to the knowledge on the system dynamics and the reflection on the ecosystem services it provides (Nedkov et al. 2023).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Case study area

Parangalitsa Reserve (Fig. 1) covers an area of 1487.29 ha (Ministry of Environment and Waters 2024) and is known for its forests of *Picea abies* L. Karst., *Abies alba* M., *Fagus sylvatica* L. that have an enormous influence over the biodiversity preservation in Bulgaria and Europe as well (Ivanov and Tyufekchiev 2019). Forests cover nearly 250 ha and are situated in altitudes between 1450 and 1950 m (Dountchev et al. 2016). Some of the Norway spruce trees reach

Figure 1. Case study area—Parangalitsa Reserve. Basemap: Orthophoto 2023, retrieved from <http://www.kade.si/cgi-bin/mapserv>; World Topographic Map ESRI (2024b).

a height of 50 m and there are Silver fir old trees of age 250 years and older reaching heights of 60 m and a diameter of 1.2 m (Panayotov et al. 2016a). At lower altitudes (below 1650 m a.s.l.), the spruce is mixed with up to 70% Silver fir and up to 40% European beech, while close to the tree line, the Norway spruce is mixed with up to 20% of the Balkan endemic species Macedonian pine (*Pinus peuce* Griseb) (Asenova et al. 2019). The reserve is part of Rila National Park and is included in Natura Protected areas under both Birds and Habitats directives. All human activities are banned on the territory of the reserve, apart from protection, scientific activities, educational visits, and collecting seeds for certain needs (Council of Ministers 1933).

2.2. Methodology

The present article integrates the calculation of three indices—SMI, LAI, and NDVI. SMI and NDVI are calculated on Landsat 8 images (up to 6% cloud cover) with 30 m resolution, derived from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Earth Explorer website. The calculations were based on the Thermal Infrared Sensor (TIRS), using Band 10 (wavelength 10.6–11.19 micrometers, resolution 100 (resampled to 30) for SMI and Band 4 (Red), wavelength 0.64–0.67 micrometers and Band 5 (Near Infrared), wavelength 0.85–0.88 micrometers (USGS 2024). The data was collected for the end-summer months (August–September) over the period 2015 to 2024. Appropriate images were not available for 2016 and 2022 because they exceed the cloud cover threshold, and the data produced is not reliable. Therefore, these years were not included in the analysis and the statistical calculations as well. LAI was calculated based on Sentinel 2 MSI satellite imagery (Copernicus 2021) for the same period 2015–2024, August–September (up to 6% cloud cover), 10-meter resolution by using Sentinel Applications Platform (SNAP) and its built-in Biophysical processor. The rasters were temporally aligned to the greatest extent possible, prioritizing cloud-free images. To match the spatial resolution, LAI was resampled (Data Management Tools) to a 30-meter pixel size by using the nearest neighbor method.

In summer, soil moisture content usually decreases due to evapotranspiration and increased temperature. Therefore, calculating SMI, NDVI and LAI during late summer (August–September) when moisture levels are lower due to peak temperatures and lower precipitation is chosen for detection of changes in the indices when moisture deficit impacts on spruce forest canopy vigor are most prominent (Yu et al. 2021).

The indices values are integrated to indicate territories within the Parangalitsa Reserve that show unstable values for these three parameters in the period 2015–2024. For this purpose, a framework that includes a workflow with three distinguished stages—Data preparation, Index calculation and Identifying deviations was elaborated (Fig. 2).

After the images were collected the calculation of the indices was performed. SMI is calculated using remote sensing methods that utilize thermal infrared temperature data alongside NDVI measurements to infer surface soil water content (Carlson et al. 1994). Studies show Land Surface Temperature (LST) derived from the thermal infrared part of the electromagnetic spectrum, and NDVI calculated using visible and near-infrared reflectance from the Earth's

Figure 2. Methodological framework.

surface is an effective technique for estimating the soil moisture (Entezari et al. 2019; Sichugova and Fazilova 2022).

The calculations, based on the combination of the NDVI and LST are as follows (Wang et al. 2015; Saha et al. 2018; Entezari et al. 2019; Tajudin et al. 2021; Sichugova and Fazilova 2022) (eq. 1):

$$SMI = (LST_{max} - LST) / (LST_{max} - LST_{min}) \text{ (eq. 1)}$$

Where:

LST_{max} / LST_{min} represent the maximum and minimum surface temperature
LST refers to the land surface temperature. LST is calculated as (eq. 2):

$$LST = T_b / [1 + (\alpha * T_b / C_2) * \ln(\epsilon)] \text{ (eq. 2)}$$

Where:

T_b (in °C) is the satellite brightness temperature

α is the wavelength of emitted radiance

C_2 is a constant (1.4388)

ε is the emissivity of the surface. The satellite brightness temperature T_b is derived from (eq. 3):

$$Tb = (K_2 / (\ln(K_1/L) + 1)) - 273.15 \text{ (eq. 3)}$$

Where:

K_1 is sensor dependent calibration constant 1 (774.8853)

K_2 is sensor dependent calibration constant 2 (1321.0789)

L is the Top of Atmosphere (TOA) spectral radiance, Pv (5) and CV is the correction value for Landsat Images (0.986).

$$\varepsilon = 0.004 * Pv + CV$$

Where Pv is the fractional vegetation cover, computed as (eq. 4):

$$Pv = ((NDVI - NDVI_{min}) / (NDVI_{max} - NDVI_{min}))^2 \text{ (eq. 4)}$$

CV is a correction value for Landsat images (typically 0.986).

NDVI is defined as the ratio of reflectivity differences between NIR and the Red band to their sum. NDVI is calculated using eq. 5:

$$NDVI = (NIR - Red) / (NIR + Red) \text{ (eq. 5)}$$

Where:

NIR is the reflectance in the near-infrared band (Band 5)

Red is the reflectance in the red band (Band 4)

The result values range from 0 to 1, where values near 1 present a higher level of soil moisture and values near 0 are the areas with low levels of soil moisture (Saha et al. 2019). All the calculations are carried out using the Raster Calculator in ArcGIS Pro 3.2.0.

LAI was calculated based on the Sentinel Applications Platform (SNAP) and its built-in Biophysical processor. Although the accuracy of LAI retrieval using Sentinel 2 can vary and is still to be improved (Kganyago et al. 2020; Mourad et al. 2020; Hassanpour et al. 2024), the use of this workflow is considered appropriate for the present study because of the suitable spatial resolution and the high spectral sensitivity that improves the detection of forest health (Chrysafis et al. 2020).

The rasters were temporally aligned to the greatest extent possible, prioritizing cloud-free images. To match the spatial resolution, the LAI index was resampled to a 30-meter pixel size to correspond with the SMI resolution.

Once all three indices were generated and aligned, a table containing the values for each cell across the three indices was extracted using the Sample tool (Spatial Analyst Tools). The relationships between LAI and SMI, as well as LAI and NDVI, were analyzed to assess the direction and strength of their

linear correlation. Pearson's Correlation Coefficient was calculated in Excel to quantify these relationships. The correlation between SMI and NDVI was not performed, as NDVI is a component of the SMI calculation.

The indices are also examined in relation to meteorological data (Meteoblue 2022). Daily data for temperature, precipitation and relative humidity was used to calculate the monthly average values for August, where most of the images are obtained. They are related to the average values of the indices for the period 2015–2021.

The next stage of the data processing is calculating the standard deviation in the results. The Sample tool in ArcGISPro 3.2.0 is used to extract the values of each index for the period 2015–2024 to a point feature class. Next, the standard deviation is calculated for each point to outline the variability of the index for this exact cell. The results were then classified into ten classes using the Jenks Natural breaks algorithm that minimizes the average deviation of a class from its mean while maximizing the deviation from the means of the other classes (Jenks 1967). The class with the highest values for each index is selected. The territories characterized by the greatest variations of NDVI, SMI and LAI are analyzed against their slope, aspect and land cover to look for patterns and consistencies.

3. Results

The results from the data processing and spatial analysis explore the relations between the vegetation and moisture indices to verify their strength and direction. This is important for the further analysis and conclusions made. The research then moves on to investigating the spatial and temporal variability of these parameters, looking for persistent patterns that may indicate ongoing ecological changes.

LAI shows deviations from 0.027 to 7.086 throughout the years (Fig. 3). The index covers the whole territory of the reserve which includes dense spruce forests situated mainly in the west part where the index values are above 3 and reach their peak of 6 and even 7 in 2023 and 2024. The eastern parts of Parangalitsa Reserve include mountain peaks of above 2400 m a.s.l. covered by rocks, grasses or bare soils. The index values there are hardly above 0.

The NDVI values range from 0.049 to 0.576, reflecting significant variation due to the diverse vegetation cover across the territories studied (Fig. 4).

SMI varies from 0.286, the lowest value calculated for 2021 to 0.846 in 2024 (Fig. 5). The years with the highest detected levels of soil moisture are 2020, 2019 and 2024. The spatial distribution of soil moisture corresponds to the vegetation cover—the forest territories characterize with the highest soil moisture while the bare soil and rocky hills occupying the western borders and central part of the reserve are assigned with lowest index values, varying from 0.286 to over 0.5. Indeed in 2021 and 2023, the highest soil moisture index values are equal to the lowest SMI in 2018–2020.

The correlation analysis (Table 1) shows a relation between the indices varying from 0.26 to 0.55 for SMI/LAI (Fig. 7) and 0.5 to 0.69 for NDVI/LAI (Fig. 6). For these calculations are used more than 30 000 records for each year, so $p < 0.001$.

Figure 3. Leaf Area Index 2015–2024.

Figure 4. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index 2015–2024.

Figure 5. Soil Moisture Index 2015–2024.

Table 1. Pearson correlation coefficient measuring the linear correlation between SMI/LAI and between NDVI/LAI for the period 2015–2024.

Year	SMI/LAI	NDVI/LAI
2015	0.433	0.574
2017	0.421	0.554
2018	0.262	0.528
2019	0.502	0.619
2020	0.473	0.498
2021	0.553	0.544
2023	0.393	0.686
2024	0.509	0.636

Figure 6. Relationship between NDVI and LAI.

The standard deviation of the values for LAI ranges from 0 (identical values for all years) to 1.94. The class of points with the highest variability ranges from 1.36 to 1.94 which suggests that there are significant differences between the values in the dataset for these exact cells. These variations of the index are detected in the dense forested parts of the reserve, that cover its southwestern and northern border. Parts of these territories are open areas that are surrounded by dense forests. Variations are also detected along the river streams.

Figure 7. Relationship between LAI and SMI.

The standard deviation of SMI values is less pronounced, with the highest variability ranging from 0.12 to 1.11. The territories exhibiting the most significant variations during this period are larger in size and predominantly cover the forested areas in the northwestern parts of the reserve. Additionally, the north-eastern section of the reserve stands out as another zone of notable variation, characterized by a mix of forests, shrubs, and rocky terrain.

The values of the NDVI prove to be most stable in that period indicating the highest variation of 0.05 to 0.08 (Fig. 8). NDVI is most unstable in the dense forests explicitly located in the northern parts of the reserve.

Climate parameter values are indicative of drought conditions in 2021, characterized by high average temperatures, low precipitation, and extremely low relative humidity (Table 2). This is consistent with the SMI mean values for the entire territory, which were notably low. The LAI values also reflect the impact of these drought conditions. However, NDVI values remain relatively high, which may be attributed to a delayed vegetation response to climatic stress. In 2017, lower temperatures and relative humidity are observed. The average precipitation values for the period appear relatively high; however, a closer analysis of the daily data reveals that this is primarily due to a single significant rainfall event of

Figure 8. Standard deviation for LAI, SMI and NDVI for the period 2015–2024.

Table 2. Monthly average values of temperature, precipitation, and relative humidity for August (2015–2021), compared to the mean values of LAI, SMI, and NDVI. Data sourced from NEMS4 Weather Model (Meteoblue 2022).

Year	Temperature (°C)	Precipitation (mm)	Relative humidity (%)	LAI	SMI	NDVI
2015	20.02	2.86	64.33	2.1247	0.6348	0.3376
2017	20.55	2.60	56.89	1.7993	0.5960	0.2970
2018	20.13	3.23	63.02	1.9989	0.6907	0.3121
2019	20.97	0.90	56.13	2.2999	0.6924	0.3724
2020	20.59	3.94	64.43	2.0175	0.6930	0.3121
2021	22.22	1.74	47.97	1.9025	0.4362	0.3715

33.2 mm on August 29, 2017. Well correlated with this are the mean values of the three indices that all exhibit low values, especially the SMI and LAI.

More than half of the territories with variations of SMI are located on a northern slope (Fig. 9). Likewise, NDVI varies most on the northern (44%), northwestern (22%) and western slopes (15%). The LAI is most unstable on the western (38%) and northwestern slopes (22%).

The inclination of the slope was also considered in the analysis. The most significant deviations occur on slopes with inclinations between 45° and 90°, where over 50% of the points exhibit the highest deviations for both NDVI and SMI, and 36.5% of the locations show the greatest deviations in LAI. In contrast, areas with inclinations below 15° account for less than 10% of all deviations.

The most distinct clusters of fluctuations in the values are located in the most south-western part of the reserve in two adjacent territorial units. According to the Forest Management Plan (Agrolesproject Ltd 2015) the first unit is with a northern aspect and inclination of 30° covered predominantly with coniferous forests of Norway spruce and Silver fir. The Silver fir trees are 150 years of age with an average height of 28 m. The growing stock volume per hectare for the Silver fir trees in this unit is 553 and for the Norway spruce—216 m³/ha.

Figure 9. Territories with the greatest variability of LAI, SMI and NDVI for the period 2015–2024. Basemap: ESRI (2024a).

The underlying material is granite, the soil is indicated as medium-rich. The second unit is a smaller, northwestern aspect, 26° inclination, mostly covered with 200 years of Norway spruce and some Scots pine.

4. Discussion

Remote sensing vegetation indices have certain limitations when studying coniferous forests since canopy structure, shadowing, and needle architecture can distort results (Zhu and Liu 2015; Rautiainen et al. 2018). Nevertheless, they have proved to be useful in understanding regional forest dynamics and degradation trends (Main-Knorn et al. 2013), changes in forest structure, forest succession and disturbances (Cohen and Goward 2004), phenological shifts, forest growth, and responses to climatic variability (Pettorelli et al. 2005). LAI has a significant contribution in assessing forest productivity, canopy structure, ecosystem processes (Asner et al. 2003) and responses to disturbances (Chen and Black 1992). Soil moisture indices play an important role in monitoring forest productivity and tracking changes in forest dynamics over time, particularly in response to droughts and seasonal fluctuations (Belmonte et al. 2022). Therefore, exploring the combination of SMI, NDVI and LAI for temporal and spatial understanding of forest dynamics is a logical step for applying remote sensing in forest monitoring. A very important aspect that has to be considered

is the different satellite platforms used for the calculation of the indices and the fact that the images used are all from the end of the summer period, but for some of them there is a temporal gap of weeks or months. This temporal gap could reflect different stages of vegetation vigor and soil moisture availability, affecting the strength of the correlation. That is why the present research first determines the relation of LAI/SMI and LAI/NDVI to verify that there are no discrepancies in the data. Parangalitsa Reserve includes dense coniferous forests, open spaces with shrubs and grasses as well as rocky areas covering a steep terrain. The territory encompasses a variety of landscape conditions that could help test the logic of the result and the behavior of the three indices in different ecosystems. The correlation analysis showed that LAI/SMI and LAI/NDVI are positively and moderately correlated (Ratner 2009). Other studies confirm the LAI-SMI relationship and explain its strength with the content of sand and clay in soils (Liu et al. 2016). The calculations indicate the relation between LAI and NDVI is stronger but still not high. Studies explain that this relation is high at lower to moderate canopy densities (Turner et al. 1999) which is not the case in Parangalitsa. Having this in mind the results from the correlation of the indices are logical, consistent with prior studies and indicate that they complement each other by combining diverse information, rather than merely overlapping data points. The highest values of LAI (7.086) are indicative of a dense, mature coniferous forest with high leaf biomass, which may contribute significantly to the forest's productivity and carbon sequestration capacity. Coniferous forests, particularly mature or old-growth stands of species like *Picea abies* (Norway spruce) or *Pinus sylvestris* (Scots pine), have LAI values in this range, especially in highly productive areas (Chen and Black 1992). The NDVI values range from 0.049 to 0.576. Notably, areas with the most vigorous vegetation, those scoring 0.5 and above are primarily non-forest regions that remain lush and green even at the end of summer at this altitude. The southeastern and northern border territories of the reserve, dominated by Norway spruce forests, exhibit an average NDVI index of 0.2 to 0.4. This corresponds to the study of Klimavičius et al. (2023) which explains that coniferous forests have the lowest maximum greenness during the summer months with NDVI values not exceeding 0.4. The SMI values indicate the greatest concentration of soil moisture explicitly in the forest areas. In terms of spatial distribution LAI's highest values are highly concentrated in the densest forest territories, open spaces within the forest areas and along the rivers' streams. As it was mentioned, NDVI's highest values are detected in open areas with grass and shrubs. And SMI highest values, calculated based on LST and emissivity, are tightly related to the dense forest vegetation areas. Hence, these three indicators interpret vegetation vigor in different ways for this specific territory with diverse land-cover. This makes the temporal variation of these indices most intriguing. The observed dependence on the slope inclination and aspect may be taken into consideration when identifying the impact of the variability of environmental conditions. The analysis of the relation with the weather parameters confirms that drought conditions generally lead to lower indices' values, although the relation is not always straightforward. The vegetation may have lagged response to climate stress or the weather conditions outside this timeframe may affect the moisture accumulation. Therefore, a longer series of data needs to be used to make a proper correlation.

Overlaying these “hesitations” across the three indices highlights areas that may be experiencing changes in the state, structure, and health of the vegetation cover. The results highlighted areas that suffered from windthrows in the period 1997–2013 (Panayotov et al. 2015). A study by Asenova et al. (2019) combines terrain and remote sensing studies located exactly in the same territorial units and identifies a big gap fraction that was likely due to the very active process of gap formation in recent years. These observations on terrain confirm that the area is undergoing dynamics. To learn more about the affected vegetation parameters and state further terrain verification is needed. The framework has the potential to provide additional information for researchers and foresters in their terrain studies and help them focus their attention on problematic areas. A serious limitation of the research is the use of different satellite platforms which form a temporal gap in the indices’ results. Using high resolution images with the same sensor characteristics and temporal resolution would give better precision to the calculations.

5. Conclusion

The present research proposes a framework for the identification of areas vulnerable to environmental risk based on three indices—NDVI, LAI and SMI and their temporal and spatial variation. It suggests that the territories with high deviation in the indices may be undergoing some dynamics in the state, structure and health of the vegetation cover. This framework is applied to the Parangalitsa Reserve, characterized by unique biodiversity, almost no human activity, and a region with diverse land cover and steep terrain. The results for the standard deviation analysis for these indices during the period 2015–2024 reveal zones where index values fluctuate significantly, with low values in some years and high in others. Notably, the areas with the highest deviations overlap within coniferous forest regions, indicating potential hotspots for further in-situ observations. Analyzing the indices value and their ranges in conjunction with the land cover, slope inclination and aspect provides additional insight into the environmental conditions that impact the vegetation vigor and the way remote sensing vegetation monitoring can detect it. There is a clear pattern showing that most of the territories with the greatest deviation of the indices are located on northern slopes with big inclination. The research proves a good and logical relation for the three indices and the different potential they have in interpreting vegetation vigor for this specific territory with diverse landcover. All three indices show the greatest deviations for territories covered with mature Norway spruce and Silver fir forests with high leaf biomass on the northwestern border of the reserve. The areas with the most pronounced changes have suffered windthrows in the last 30 years. Gap fractions were also identified on terrain there by previous studies. The framework indicated forests where disturbances are indeed registered. The developed framework has the potential to contribute to forest management and ecological monitoring by providing a replicable methodology for pre-assessing sensitive ecosystems. It may serve as a tool for preliminary analysis and identification of vulnerable areas, offering a strategic foundation to guide and prioritize targeted field investigations effectively.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest was declared.

Ethical statement

No ethical statement was reported.

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Conceptualization: ET, MZ. Data curation: ET. Formal analysis: ET. Funding acquisition: MZ. Investigation: ET. Methodology: ET. Project administration: MZ. Visualization: ET. Writing - original draft: ET. Writing - review and editing: MZ.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.